

inDICES

Measuring the Impact of Digital Culture

Deliverable 5.9

Capacity Building Report

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Project co-ordinator name, Title and Organisation: Simonetta Buttò, Director of the Central Institute for the Union Catalogue of the Italian Libraries (ICCU)

Tel: +39 06 49210425

E-mail: simonetta.butto@beniculturali.it

Project website address: <http://indices-culture.eu/>

Author: **Aisha Villegas**
Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision

Contributing partners: **Frederik Truyen, KU Leuven**
Olivier Schulbaum, Platoniq
Nadia Nadesan, Platoniq
Julia Pagel, NEMO
Roxanne Lagaradère, Absiskey
Georgia Evans, Europeana Foundation
Sebastiaan ter Burg, Europeana Foundation

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Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	5
2. Introduction	6
3. Capacity Building Plan	7
3.1 Goals of the Capacity Building plan	7
3.2 Target audiences: stakeholder groups	7
3.3 Capacity Building activities	8
<i>Boot Camp</i>	8
<i>Visual Analytics Dashboard recorded tutorials and training sessions</i>	10
<i>inDICEs MOOC</i>	10
<i>Workshops</i>	11
<i>Digital Internship</i>	12
<i>Digital resources</i>	13
4. Timeline	14
5. Conclusion	15

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an overview of the Capacity Building strategy, which will be carried out during the second and third year of the inDICEs project within WP5 Dissemination, Stakeholder engagement and Exploitation. The document outlines the goals of the Capacity-Building plan and identifies and defines the target audiences of this strategy. Taken from the previous, the document defines the activities and resources that partners of the project will organize to ensure the successful use and uptake of the Open Observatory platform and outcomes of the project by target audiences. This report is the first iteration of two versions. The second version will provide the results of the activities hereby described.

2 Introduction

The main goal of inDICEs is to empower policy-makers and decision-makers in the Cultural and Creative Industries (CCI) to fully understand the social and economic impact of digitisation in their sectors and address the need for innovative (re)use of cultural assets, by tracking policies in an open observatory and establishing policy priorities for successful digital transformation and future governance of cultural and creative content ecosystems.

To this end, inDICEs is developing a unique methodology and an Open Observatory platform for CHIs and researchers where they will be able to make strategic decisions that will allow them to increase their positive contributions to the CCI and society. For their own part, policy-makers and CHI's will have a framework to assess the impact of cultural heritage and a dashboard to keep track of the advancement of the impact of cultural heritage in Europe.

To ensure the successful use and uptake of the Open Observatory platform and outcomes of the project by the target audiences, the inDICEs project proposes in this document, a Capacity Building plan.

The strategy aims to diffuse the knowledge of the research carried out under the different work packages of the project, mainly related to the cross-national legal analysis of the European IP framework applicable to the activities of CHIs, the use and reuse of cultural assets, the analysis of the value chains for CHI in the Digital Single Market (DSM), among others. Furthermore, the Capacity-Building strategy provides support to enable users to act and adopt the key propositions of the project: The Open Observatory Platform - including the Participatory space, the Analytics Dashboard and the Self Assessment tool.

The Capacity Building Strategy is completed by the communication and dissemination plan described in Deliverable 5.1, to promote and ensure engagement to the activities. For the success of promotional and communication activities of these events, and especially the achievement of the goals of the project, the collaboration and contribution of all partners is needed.

Partners are expected to use their networks, contacts, websites, and social media platforms to contribute to the overall success of capacity building events.

3 Capacity Building Plan

The capacity building plan presents the actions that will ensure the success of and the engagement in the activities and therefore, the use and uptake of the project outcomes by key target audiences.

3.1 Goals of the Capacity Building plan

The aim of the inDICEs Capacity Building plan is to diffuse the project's main research findings, as well as facilitate the use and uptake of the inDICEs key propositions by cultural institutions, policy-makers, funding agencies, researchers, practitioner networks, decision makers, as well as creatives Industries.

The identified target audience will increase their knowledge on IP licenses and copyright regulations and management, the use and reuse of cultural assets, value chains for CHIs in the Digital Single Market (DSM), and the use of collaborative platforms and innovative tools developed under the project. With this newly gained knowledge and tools, the target audiences will be able analyse and evaluate their reach and impact, as well as to develop activities that will lead to improve their impact in their field.

Additionally, target audiences will contribute to further development of the project research and tools with the different activities: boot camp, workshops, tutorials and training sessions, courses and internships, and online resources with recommendations. The activities will be offered online and in person depending on the constraints imposed by the COVID-19 anti-contagion restrictions.

3.2 Target audiences: stakeholder groups

Key target audiences are those potential early adopters of inDICEs results. As defined in the deliverable 5.1 Communication Plan, the target audience of the inDICEs project are identified and divided as follows:

- *Researchers.* research groups involved in the Social sciences and the Humanities; Cultural Economics and IP Law. Those who have particular interest in accessing data to gather insights in the Cultural and Creative sector

- *Cultural Heritage Practitioners and Institutions.* In particular major European memory institutions holding cultural assets, those who are interested in learning more about IP licenses, copyright, open access and their readiness for the DSM. These can be GLAM community (Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums)
- *Policy makers.* Decision makers involved in the creating policies in regional, national and EU level
- *Artistic, cultural and creative communities.* Artists, designers, individual makers and creative studios

3.3 Capacity Building activities

Different consortium partners will be responsible for the capacity building events organisation and coordination. The content definition of the activities are the results of the collaboration of the Consortium members. Each activity will be focusing on certain topics adapted to the needs and interests of the different target groups. Each expert will be involved in its own expertise area to animate the training and events.

The following section outlines key activities, events and contents created exclusively to facilitate the use and uptake of the inDICEs outcomes.

Boot Camp

Democratising participatory research (hybrid 2 days event combining offline and online participation)

inDICEs has developed the Participatory Space, a platform that serves as a collaborative online environment for deliberation, co-creation and transparent dialogue between cultural heritage professionals, policy-makers, researchers and creative industry representatives. In order to facilitate the uptake and use of the platform, Platoniq will host a Boot Camp with approximately 30 participants. The Boot camp will act as both a showcase and a hands on workshop event bringing together institutions, researchers, practitioners and communities of practices beyond the inDICEs core partners to extend inDICEs core values and strategies to encourage and facilitate joint research opportunities. The event will be co-organized with local communities involved in data and

technopolitics research, who have expressed interest in testing and improving inDICEs developments, particularly the integration of visual analytics in the proposals and debates processes, both on a technical and a methodological level. These local communities, such as DigitalFems (develops projects based on data science with a gender perspective applied to different topics, specially Open Data about the employment gap for women in cinema 2015-2020), DataForGoodBCN (a collective of do gooders that help other not for profit, and non-governmental, organizations harness the power of their data) or research.wikimedia.org representants, will be hosting “flash task forces” - thematic working groups of max. 6 participants - to push the participatory platform to the limit and will share their demos, including data sets and findings with online participants. Participation will be open to online communities willing to work from a distance. An open Call online will be launched a month before the event building on the experience of organising inDICEs consultation workshops.

Expected outcome: Around 40 participants will experience the value of opening their knowledge, sharing research hypotheses and data in the online environment, joining participatory processes and facilitating the onboarding of the platform as well as envisioning the sustainability of the Platform beyond the inDICEs project.

The Boot Camp will also serve as a shareback session with the Decidim¹ community (a democratic community that manages the Decidim project, the digital infrastructure behind the inDICEs Open Observatory, in all its dimensions), where all inDICEs developments will be contextualized and showcased.

The event will be hosted in Canodrom, Municipal Athenaeum of Digital and Democratic Innovation in Barcelona, as well as online using the participatory platform as a transition and documentation space.

Target audience: GLAM institutions, academic and action researchers, practitioners and communities of practices, Canodrom Residents researching digital culture.

Timing: November 2021 (TBC)

¹ <https://decidim.org/>

Visual Analytics Dashboard recorded tutorials and training sessions

The inDICEs dashboard will be made available in two different formats, (i) a simple mobile-friendly and embeddable version that requires only a limited amount of training and supports the participatory space, and (ii) a more complex desktop version for advanced users - e.g. researchers and analysts - who require advanced query definitions and want to explore content assets along multiple metadata dimensions. For the latter, inDICEs will offer a combination of recorded tutorials and training sessions to convey the required skills and maximize the adoption rate and utility of the platform.

Expected outcome: The tutorials and training sessions will serve to provide familiarity with the dashboard's interactive features, including topic definition and disambiguation to configure alerting functions and data export features. The tutorials will be made available through the inDICEs Open Observatory platform so users will be able to refer to these at a later time. The training sessions will take place in a dedicated session with invited participants. The recorded sessions will be shared on the inDICEs website.

Target audience: Dashboard users among the consortium partners as well as target audiences described above and exploitation targets.

Timing: April 2022

inDICEs MOOC

An online learning course (MOOC) will be developed by KULeuven on how to implement Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHI) Assessment Monitor.

Expected outcome: The MOOC (D5.6) will be a key instrument for the capacity building targeting Cultural Heritage Institutions. In fact it aims to bring together information from the Indices research in educational formats, that can be used for training Heritage professionals at work in the institutions as well as university students. It will focus on the indicators that individual operatives as well as organisations should monitor to be able to assess and steer their digital performance. It will run at least in 3 iterations, so also beyond the scope of the project. The MOOC will be made available on an independent platform (TBC). This will be further explained in Deliverable 5.6 "Cultural Heritage Institutions and the Digital Single Market MOOC".

Target audience: In service heritage professionals, CHI managers, training providers, cultural management researchers, university students

Timing: M28, April 2022

Workshops

A series of consultation workshops are organized throughout the project to engage a wider stakeholder community in gathering feedback which will inform the direction of the project. Additional workshops are planned to target different audiences.

1. The Consultation Workshops with Cultural Heritage Institutions

As part of task 5.4, a series of consultation workshops have been organized throughout the project with work packages 1, 2, 3 and 4. The first consultation workshop² was organized by KU Leuven (CS Digital) with two sessions on “IPR Framework for Digital Transformation in the Cultural Heritage sector³” and on “Value Chains and Impact in the Cultural Heritage Sector⁴”. The second consultation workshop⁵ was organised by CCC with two sessions on “Emergent forms of digital cultural production/re-production, participation and re-use of CHI contents in DSM⁶” and “Sharing collections sustainably and meaningfully: A brief introduction to rights management in cultural organizations⁷”. The third consultation workshop will be hosted by ICCU with the theme “Managing and Facilitating institutional Change in an era of rapid IT Change”.

Expected outcome: engage with a wider stakeholder community, gather key insights of the CHIs and feedback to inform the direction of the project, facilitate the uptake of the Open Observatory platform and its components.

Target audience: CHI and practitioners, policy makers, GLAM community

Timing: Third Consultation workshop will take place in November 2021 (TBC)

² [Information about the first Consultation Workshop](#) is available in the inDICEs Participatory Space

³ [Summary 1st session from the Consultation Workshop with the CHI Sector: Understanding Our digital Futures](#) is available on the inDICEs website

⁴ [Summary 2nd session from the 1st Consultation Workshop: Value Chains & impact in the Cultural Heritage sector](#) is available on the inDICEs website

⁵ [Information about the second Consultation Workshop](#) is available in the inDICEs Participatory Space

⁶ [Summary about this session](#) is available in the inDICEs website

⁷ [Recordings from both sessions](#) are available on the inDICEs Participatory Space

2. Online Workshop with NEMO

The online workshop will be jointly organized by NEMO and inDICEs. The event aims to target museum professionals from Europe.

Expected outcome: the online workshop aim to i) give inDICEs feedback about usability of results and processes of the Self-assessment tool and Open Observatory, ii) increase the group of flowchart users to generate more relevant data that will feed into the Self-assessment tool (value of flowchart grows with growing amount of users) iii) create a larger network of CHI to engage with inDICEs and increase the visibility of the project.

Target audience: museum professionals from Europe, from different sizes/categories of museums, from NEMO network. To be selected by NEMO and inDICEs

Timing: October 2021 (TBC). A 3 weeks course, 2 hours per week = 6 hours total.

3. Workshop at the Europeana Aggregator's FAIR

An introductory workshop took place on June 17, 2021 to test the concept of the Self-Assessment tool as a capacity building instrument for Europeana Aggregators. Video from the session is currently available at Europeana Pro⁸.

Expected outcome: The event aims to gather key feedback from Aggregators to fine-tune the Self-Assessment tool and prepare the workshops for Cultural Heritage Institutions. Dry run of the Self-assessment demo.

Target audience: Europeana Aggregators

Timing: June 17th, 2021, a 2 hours workshop

Digital Internship

Internships can offer a valuable way to build capacity in new professional(s) who are looking to work in digital cultural heritage, through developing their skills and experience. Europeana is exploring actions it can take to support new professionals in the sector following on from a New Professionals Task Force run by the Europeana Network Association, which finished in early 2021. As part of this

Kommentar [1]: EF or KULeuven

Kommentar [2]: @georgia.evans@europeana.eu

Kommentar [3]: Thank you Aisha, I have added some text!
@julia.fallon@europeana.eu
@sebastian.terburg@europeana.eu
please could you also check this.

⁸ <https://pro.europeana.eu/event/europeana-aggregators-fair>

work, Europeana will explore the potential of developing an internship related to digital skills, the inDICEs project and its partners' activities, and write recommendations on its feasibility and if and how this could be taken forward.

Expected outcome: A feasibility assessment & recommendation for running an internship programme related to the inDICEs project; based on this assessment, this could include recommendations for developing and running an internship related to inDICEs project and partners activities.

Target audience: The target audience of the internship would be explored as part of this work; the document and recommendations will be shared with project partners.

Timing: Feasibility, recommendations and next steps determined by January 2022.

Digital resources

A series of digital resources will be developed and published to share with key audiences the outcomes of the research undertaken by the different work packages of the inDICEs project. These digital resources include reports, guidelines and recommendations, made into user friendly formats such as downloadable PDFs and videos. The resources will include charts or images to illustrate and support the content and will be freely available for download on the inDICEs website and Open Observatory. These outcomes will be promoted through inDICEs channels and each partner's individual networks.

Expected outcome: The aim of the digital resources is to i) share the results and insights of the research undertaken by WP 1, 2 and 3 in a user friendly manner ii) share best practices and recommendations related to IP, copyright, licensing, as well as and use and re-use of digital cultural resources.

Target audience: Policy makers, CHIs and CHI practitioners, the GLAM community, researchers

Timing: Publication will take place in different periods throughout 2021 and 2022

4 Timeline

The table below outlines the key capacity building activities, involved target groups, and specific channels that will be used to communicate and disseminate these activities.

Estimated Month	Activity	Target Audience	Channels
2021			
June	Workshop at the Europeana Aggregator's FAIR	Europeana Aggregators	Europeana Foundation channels, inDICES social media channels
October	Online Workshop with NEMO	Museum professionals from Europe, from different sizes/categories of museums, from NEMO network. To be selected by NEMO and inDICES	NEMO channels, inDICES channels, Europeana Foundation channels. Personal invitations
November	3rd Consultation Workshop	CHI and practitioners, policy makers, GLAM community	inDICES channels (social media, mailing, website) & partners' of the project channels. Personal invitations
November	Boot Camp	GLAM institutions, academic and action researchers, practitioners and communities of practices, Canodrom Residents researching digital culture.	Platoniq channels, inDICES channels (social media, mailing, website) & partners' of the project channels. Personal invitations
2022			
January	Digital internship	The target audience of the internship TBC	Europeana Foundation channels
April	Visual Analytics Dashboard recorded tutorials and training sessions	Dashboard users among the consortium partners as well as external stakeholders and exploitation targets	WebLyzard and inDICES channels, personal invitations
April 2022 (M28)	MOOC	In service heritage professionals, CHI managers, training providers, cultural management researchers, university	KULeuven and inDICES channels

		students	
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5 Conclusion

In conclusion, the deliverable identifies and presents an overview of the Capacity-Building plan that aims to facilitate the diffuse and active engagement with the project's main research findings, as well as facilitate the use and uptake of the inDICEs key propositions by cultural institutions, policy-makers, funding agencies, researchers, practitioner networks, decision makers, as well as creatives Industries. The activities and resources described in the document are crucial to ensure the successful use of the Open Observatory platform and outcomes of the project by target audiences. This document serves as the first version and will be updated with the results of the Capacity-Building plan in month 36.